

Book Review

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Organic chemistry is an important subarea of chemistry discipline that has been taught in the course curriculum of all the Universities in the country. Sachin Kumar Ghosh's "Advanced General Organic Chemistry" is a comprehensive textbook for the undergraduate level of organic chemistry. The first edition of this textbook was published in 1986. Mr. Ghosh has long teaching experience in New Alipore College and an inspiring chemistry teacher. In the latest edition (third edition) of Ghosh's classic textbook, the basic contents of the earlier editions are retained. Nevertheless, many sections have been updated and some of them have been rearranged.

The book consists of 23-chapters with a total number of 1813 pages, which have been organized into two parts. First part of the book contains seventeen chapters. The opening chapter provides a brief overview about the importance of organic molecules and stepwise approach to study them. The structure, classification and nomenclature of the organic molecules are discussed subsequently (Chapters 2 and 3). All the conceptual background that would be essential to understand the basic reactivity of organic molecules and reaction mechanism are covered in chapters 4-8. The fundamental of stereochemistry of organic molecules is discussed in chapter 9. The preliminary discussion of the modern spectroscopic

techniques such as UV-Visible, IR and ^1H NMR are covered in chapter 10 with an objective to provide a basic idea about the different methods of characterization of organic molecules. The remaining seven chapters of Part I deal with the actual core of the subject including reaction mechanisms, rearrangements, addition reactions, elimination reactions and substitution reactions. Part II (Chapters 18-22) consists of the chemistry of hydrocarbons, heterocyclic compounds, functional-groups, amino acids and peptides, carbohydrates along with a separate chapter for the planning of synthesis. These are followed by five appendices. The book finishes with a subject index, named topic index and compound index.

Although the book covers most of the areas of the subject, the basics of catalysis (homogeneous as well as heterogeneous) and its usefulness in organic chemistry could be included before the core chapters. The discussion on the method of determining reaction mechanism in chapter 11 is weak. The Curtin-Hammett principle may be discussed in details with proper examples. The discussion on chirality of heteroatom (molecules having chiral center other than carbon atom) is not included in chapter 9. Few examples of such class of chiral molecules may be added and the concept of planar and helical chirality could be discussed in details. According to this reviewer, the reorganization of some chapters may be useful for the readers. Accordingly, the chapter 18 (chemistry of hydrocarbons) could be shifted to Part I before the chapter 17 (aromatic electrophilic substitutions), the chapter 16 (reactions involving C=O) may be placed in Part II before the chapter 20 (chemistry of functional groups) and the chapter 19 (a few heterocyclic compounds) may be discussed subsequently. The chapter 21 (planning of synthesis) could be the final chapter of the book. The appendix E may be merged with the chapter 10. The discussion on green chemistry in appendix D could be improved. The ap-

pendix B and C may be omitted or reduced. A separate chapter may be dedicated to the fundamentals of stereoselective organic synthesis dealing with different stereochemical models such as Cram model, Felkin-Anh model, Zimmerman-Traxler model etc. Few spelling and structural errors are appeared in different sections of the book, which could be eliminated after a careful proof-reading. Additionally, the improvement on print and page quality of the book may be required.

In summary, the level of presentation of the book is very

clear. It will be appropriate to both the students and other practitioners of the subject.

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